

Studies on the Ion-selective Behaviour of Anion Exchange 'Neosepta' Membrane as Electrode

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Manuscript received 12 January 1995, revised 26 July 1995, accepted 30 November 1995

Ion exchange membranes of 'Neosepta' type prepared by Mizutani *et al.*¹ mainly for the commercial utilisation of desalination of sea water in Japan have also been found to respond as suitable membrane electrodes². Recently Mizutani *et al.*³ have claimed that one variety of these membranes prepared by incorporating suitable reagents have been found to separate univalent ions from bivalent ions in the desalination process. The present work is intended to explore the future possibility of utilising these membranes as univalent ion-selective electrodes.

The selectivity constant (K_{ps}) used to study the ion-selective behaviour of a membrane can be calculated using the empirical equation of Nicolskii⁴,

$$E = E_0 - RT/F \ln [a_p + K_{ps} a_s^{1/2}] \quad (1)$$

where, E_0 stands for $RT/F \ln a_p^I$ with the activity value, a_p^I of the univalent primary ion p on one side of the membrane fixed for a particular set of experiments, and a_p and a_s are the activity values of the primary ion p and of the secondary interfering bivalent ion s on the other side of the membrane. For the separate solution method using the same activity values of p and s ions on the two sides of the membrane the basic equation is simplified to the form,

$$E = (RT/F) \ln [a_p^{1/2}/K_{ps}] \quad (2)$$

and K_{ps} values are calculated from the known values of E and a_p . For mixed solution method the working formula appears as

$$\exp(E_1 - E_2)/(RT/F) a_p - a'_p = K_{ps} a_s^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

Plots of left-hand-side of equation (3) against a_s should be linear with slope K_{ps} .

Results and Discussion

In separate solution method the activity range used are 3×10^{-4} to 243×10^{-4} with the ratio 1 : 3 in the successive values. Calculated values of K_{ps} using equation (2) (Table 1) show that $K_{ps} \ll 1$, indicating the halide specificity for the ACS membrane. However, the values are not exactly constant over the concentration range studied but have increasing tendency towards higher concentrations. The variation in the selectivity constant values have also been noted with commercial electrodes by earlier workers^{5,6}.

Fig. 1. The deviations of experimental potentials from theoretical Nernst potential (O, Δ, □, ◇) due to interference of the sulphate ion at varying concentrations with iodide form ACS membrane at different initial concentrations : (O) 480×10^{-4} , (Δ) 146×10^{-4} , (□) 45×10^{-4} and (◇) 15×10^{-4} of iodide ion.

Closer scrutiny of Table 1 also shows that the iodide ion has the highest specificity maintaining an order $I^- > Br^- > Cl^-$ in presence of either SO_4^{2-} or Ox^{2-} ions.

TABLE 1—CALCULATED VALUES OF K_{ps} OF DIFFERENT HALIDES IN PRESENCE OF SULPHATE/OXALATE BY SEPARATE SOLUTION METHOD WITH EQUAL ACTIVITY ON BOTH SIDES OF THE ACS MEMBRANE (VIDE EQN. 2)

a $\times 10^4$	$K_{ps} \times 10^3 (SO_4^{2-})$			$K_{ps} \times 10^3 (Ox^{2-})$		
	I ⁻	Br ⁻	Cl ⁻	I ⁻	Br ⁻	Cl ⁻
3	2	7	19	2	5	22
9	3	12	26	3	8	27
27	5	20	42	4	13	32
81	8	34	73	7	22	54
243	13	58	126	12	38	94

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In case of mixed solution method, the fixed molalities of the halide ions in the mixture for different sets of experiments vary from 5×10^{-4} to 480×10^{-4} , and for each set the

Fig. 2 Tolerance limits of concentrations of interfering sulphate (A) and of oxalate (B) by iodide, bromide and chloride form membranes at their different initial concentrations; the lowest line in (A) is due to non-specific MA membrane (I^-) shown for comparison.

molalities of the bivalent interferrant vary from 2×10^{-4} to 400×10^{-4} in the mixture. Fig. 1 displays the influence of interferrant, where the experimental potentials in the mixture are compared with the corresponding theoretical Nernst potentials calculated taking into consideration the successive changes in the ionic strength of the medium. This figure reveals the most important point that the primary ion concentration levels play very important role.

The 'tolerance limits' showing the highest concentration of the interferrant upto which Nernst potential of the primary ion can be measured ignoring the presence of secondary ion with error much less than 1% are shown in the Fig. 2 with bivalent interferrants SO_4^{2-} and Ox^{2-} and the data in Table 2 for perusal in details. The results indicate that the relative proportions of the primary and the secondary ions are very important for finding the specificity. The tolerance limits markedly varying among the halide ions show the order $\text{I}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{Cl}^-$.

TABLE 2—TOLERANCE LIMITS OF THE CONCENTRATIONS OF SULPHATE AND OXALATE WITH DIFFERENT HALIDE FORM ACS MEMBRANE IN EACH SET WITH DECREASE IN INITIAL CONCENTRATION OF THE HALIDE IONS

Halide $\times 10^4 M$	$m \times 10^4 (\text{SO}_4^{2-})$			$m \times 10^4 (\text{Ox}^{2-})$		
	I^-	Br^-	Cl^-	I^-	Br^-	Cl^-
480	390	300	100	96	22	7
146	120	95	30	30	8	3
45	40	35	10	10	4	1
15	12	5	3	5	2	0.5

The calculated values of K_{ps} in mixed solutions from the slopes of the plots using the equation (3) (Table 3) show that the values are much less than 1 justifying the claim of Mizutani *et al.* that ACS membrane has much higher selectivity for the halide ions than the bivalent sulphate or oxalate, which, however, maintain the order $\text{I}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{Cl}^-$ with better performance in presence of sulphate. It is also seen that the values are not exactly constant but slightly change depending upon the relative proportions of the primary and interfering ions in the mixture supporting the warning of Moody and Thomas⁵ that mere statement of the value of the selectivity constant is somewhat misleading and one should properly mention the relative proportions. Srinivasan and Rechnitz⁶ also observed these changes with commercially available electrodes. It is also seen that values from the separate solution method (Table 1) and from the mixed solution method (Table 2) are not exactly on a par. The earlier investigators^{3,7} suggested that the values found with the mixed solution method should be given more importance since from the viewpoint of practical application it is more realistic than the separate solution method.

TABLE 3—AVERAGE K_{ps} VALUES BY THE MIXED SOLUTION METHOD CALCULATED FROM SLOPES OF THE PLOTS (EQN. 3)

Halide $\times 10^4 M$	$K_{\text{ps}} \times 10^3 (\text{SO}_4^{2-})$			$K_{\text{ps}} \times 10^3 (\text{Ox}^{2-})$		
	I^-	Br^-	Cl^-	I^-	Br^-	Cl^-
480	1	2	6	4	6	10
146	1	3	6	4	6	10
45	1	3	9	5	6	10
15	2	3	10	5	6	20
5	2	4	—	6	7	—

Moody and Thomas⁵ suggested a formula for the calculation of percentage error incurred in the estimation of primary ion activity with a particular K_{ps} value when the relative activity levels change,

$$\text{Percentage error} = \frac{100 K_{\text{ps}} a_s^{1/2}}{a_p} \quad (4)$$

Table 4 showing a set of calculations with different activity levels of p^- and s^{2-} ions clearly reflects that when the p^- ion level is higher or comparable with that of s^{2-} ions, the error is much less than 1% but increase with higher activity values of s^{2-} ion. For the same activity ratio the less percentage errors incurred with the small K_{ps} values can also be found from the values of iodide, bromide and chloride showing the selectivity order $\text{I}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{Cl}^-$. The exact reason for the low response to bivalent ions is not known. It may only be speculated that because of introduction of *m*-phenylenediamine into the base membrane the transport behaviours of the bivalent ions have been greatly reduced, which have already been established by studying the electrical resistance in the sulphate and halide forms of the membranes³.

TABLE 4—CALCULATED PERCENTAGE ERROR USING EQN. 4 WHEN THE RELATIVE ACTIVITY LEVELS CHANGE WITH THE AVERAGE K_{ps} VALUES 0.001, 0.003, AND 0.006 FOR IODIDE, BROMIDE AND CHLORIDE RESPECTIVELY

Activity level (mixture)		% Error			
Halide $\times 10^4$	$SO_4 \times 10^4$	I^-	Br^-	Cl^-	
390	148	0.3	0.9	1.8	
	45	0.2	0.5	1.0	
	20	0.1	0.3	0.7	
130	148	0.9	3.8	5.6	
	45	0.5	1.5	3.1	
	20	0.3	1.0	2.1	
4	148	3.0	9.0	18	
	45	1.6	5.0	10	
	20	1.1	3.4	6.7	

Experimental

The anion exchange selective membrane ACS of 'Neosepta' family, received as a 'gift sample', had the following characteristics: thickness 0.18–0.2 mm, water content 0.3–0.4 g H_2O/g in Cl^- -form, electrical resistance 4–5 Ωcm^2 at 25° with Cl^- -form membrane, and exchange capacity 1.5–2.0 meq/g Cl^- -form membrane. Membrane attachment and the setting up of the electrode vessel for the measurement were done by the usual techniques². The e.m.f.s were read at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ within ± 0.1 mV with a Cambridge potentiometer fitted with a suspended coil galvanometer having a current sensitivity of 10^{-10} A/mm/m. The cell arrangement was as follows:

where, SCE is the saturated calomel electrode. Standard

solutions of chloride, bromide, iodide, sulphate and oxalate were prepared with G.R. (E. Merck) grade potassium salts using double-distilled conductivity water. The molalities of the solutions were so prepared that the activities of the solutions were from 1×10^{-4} to 729×10^{-4} maintaining 1 : 3 between the successive solutions to minimise the deviations from the usual Nernst potentials². During the experimental measurements both the solutions on two sides, either in the separate solution method or in the mixture on one side were stirred magnetically with a cork pad under the electrode set-up to offset the undesirable thermal effect. The solutions on both sides were intermittently changed before recording the steady potentials, and the average value of three readings within 0.5% of each other was accepted.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their sincere gratitude to Dr. Yukio Mizutani, Fujisawa Research Laboratory, Japan, for the gift sample of the membranes. Thanks are also due to the University of Burdwan for financial assistance and facilities.

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